

IMPROVING ECOLOGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

Urinov Shokir,
Military Institute of Information Technologies and Communications of the
Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Urinova Xulkar Shokirovna
Navoi State University of Mining and Technology

Abstract: The article discusses the issues of ecological stabilization and improvement of environmental protection. A significant increase in production in our country leads to a high level of environmental pollution in our republic, and the analysis of the socio-economic and ecological situation has revealed to us the main direction to eliminate the environmental crisis.

Key words: ecology, environmental protection, improvement, sustainability.

The current ecological crisis threatens the possibilities of sustainable development of human civilization. Further degradation of natural systems leads to destabilization of the biosphere, loss of its integrity and the ability to maintain the quality of the environment necessary for life. Overcoming the crisis is possible only on the basis of the formation of a new type of relationship between man and nature, in accordance with the adaptive capacity of natural systems, excluding the possibility of destruction and destruction of the natural environment.

Sustainable development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, improving the quality of life and health of its residents, as well as ensuring national security and improving the environment, affecting the development of all aspects of the country's life and implementing the principles of environmental protection and sustainable use of natural resources in the national system of socio-economic relations requires the formation and consistent implementation of the state environmental policy that ensures the increase. Ecological crisis means a situation in the relationship between society and nature, in

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which there are contradictions between the economy and ecology, the economic interests of society in consuming and using the natural environment, and environmental requirements for ensuring the protection of nature.

There are two components of the ecological crisis situation - natural and social. The natural component of the ecological crisis indicates the deterioration and destruction of the natural environment surrounding man. The social component of the ecological crisis (even if the ecological crisis is a social phenomenon in general) is the inability of state and public structures to stop environmental degradation, stabilize the situation, and improve the natural environment.

A significant increase in production throughout the country has led to a high level of environmental pollution in the country. Attempts to stabilize the environmental situation at the republican level were scattered and did not achieve great results. The reason for this is the lack of effective levers and incentives to increase the interest of enterprises in the rational and integrated use of natural resources and reduce environmental pollution, and the lack of appropriate powers and necessary funds of local authorities.

As a result, the greening of production and other sectors of the economy continues: the relative emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere and discharge into water bodies are increasing. Irrational and sometimes predatory use of natural resources contributes to the destruction of natural complexes. Low or almost non-existent payment rates for natural resources contribute to the overexploitation of natural resources, which undermines the reproduction of renewable resources.

The modern socially determined environmental policy of our country is aimed at improving and developing the services of studying, predicting, identifying, monitoring, and warning the population of emergency situations; scientifically and methodically justifying the development of plans for preventive measures to protect the population and minimize preventable damages; regulation of economic and other activities in areas prone to natural and man-made emergencies in order to minimize unavoidable and avoidable damages; prevention of man-made emergency situations; development

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of services for emergency situations and their consequences. In order to prevent the deterioration of the ecological situation and bring the state of environmental components to the standard level, it is necessary to conduct a targeted environmental policy based on the principles of market relations and using the financial and economic opportunities of all.

The analysis of the socio-economic and ecological situation of our country allows us to identify five main directions for eliminating the ecological crisis. The first direction is usually the improvement of technology. This is a technological direction: creation of environmentally friendly technology, introduction of waste-free, low-waste production, renewal of basic funds, improvement of technological processes. The second direction is related to the development and improvement of the economic mechanism of environmental protection. The economic direction solves the main problem - to make environmental protection an integral part of production and commercial activities, so that the entrepreneur, the manager of the economy is no less interested in environmental protection than in the production of competitive products. The third direction is the application of administrative action measures and legal liability measures for violations (administrative-legal direction), i.e. suspending and terminating the activities of enterprises that violate environmental laws, bringing administrative, civil and criminal liability for violation of laws and damage to the natural environment. The fourth direction is to harmonize the ecological structure. This is the direction of ecological education, it is the development of ecological education, enlightenment, educational system, reconstruction of consumers' attitude to nature. The fifth direction is the harmonization of international environmental relations, showing ways out of the ecological crisis.

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